

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/251879098>

A Study on Genetic Distances Among Germplasm Accessions of French Bean

Article · January 2008

Source: PubMed

CITATIONS

0

READS

73

1 author:

Deepu Mathew

Kerala Agricultural University

64 PUBLICATIONS 53 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

KSCSTE Young Investigators Programme in Biotechnology - Research Project - Accelerated breeding for anthracnose resistance in vegetable cowpea through molecular marker assisted selection [View project](#)

DBT Proect - MARKER ASSISTED BREEDING TO DEVELOP A BACTERIAL WILT RESISTANT CHILLI PAPRIKA VARIETY (*Capsicum annum* L.) SUITED FOR THE TROPICAL REGIONS OF INDIA [View project](#)

All content following this page was uploaded by [Deepu Mathew](#) on 30 July 2017.

The user has requested enhancement of the downloaded file.

A Study on Genetic Distances Among Germplasm Accessions of French Bean

Deepu Mathew* [Assistant Professor]

Deepu Mathew: deepuhort@gmail.com

*Kerala Agricultural University, Tavanur 679573, India

Abstract

In a usual hierarchical cluster analysis, the identification of genetic distances among germplasm accessions through morphological data on qualitative as well as quantitative characters recorded using the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI)/ National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR) descriptors, the high numerical nature of the quantitative data leads to the masking of smaller numerical but very important qualitative characters, leading to a lesser precision. This is true with D^2 statistics and also the principal component based vector analysis leading to genetic divergence, restricting the use of highly significant qualitative parameters in germplasm characterization, often resulting in misclassifications even at the species level. Hence, the molecular markers are relied upon for final conclusions. Efficient data transformation systems to arrive at the exact genetic distances by accounting for both the qualitative as well as quantitative characters with equal weightage are being detailed hereunder. Among the models proposed, (value – mean)/SD was proved to be the best and the results are further supported by the factor analysis of principal components derived from the correlation matrix.

Keywords

Factor analysis; Genetic distance; Hierarchical cluster; Morphological descriptor; *Phaseolus vulgaris*; Principal components; Transformation

Introduction

Augmented designs (Federer, 1956; and Sapra and Agarwal, 1992) are recommended for the evaluation of germplasm accessions through standardized morphological descriptors designed by the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR) (Srivastava *et al.*, 2001), which act as tools for revealing the superiority of a particular accession over the existing ones with reference to the character of interest rather than revealing the cumulative genetic distances among the accessions. Cluster analysis (Falconer, 1989) as well as D^2 statistics (Mahalanobis, 1928 and 1936) establish the comparative distance among the accessions by simultaneously considering the maximum possible morphological characters. Clustering based on a single character is proved to be exact (Sharma, 1978) in these techniques and the molecular support for the same was provided through randomly amplified polymorphic DNA analysis (Mathew, 2004). However, hierarchical clustering through morphological data on the maximum possible characters recorded using standard descriptors was proved to be less precise since the simultaneous usage of qualitative and quantitative characters leads to the masking of qualitative data by the latter with the weightage arising out of its higher numerical nature; for which D^2 statistics is also not an exception (Chandrasekharaiah *et al.*, 1969). The methodology for transformation of morphological data to avoid this problem and to ensure equal consideration for both in a hierarchical clustering is being discussed.

Materials and Methods

Thirteen pre-identified (stability of expression) accessions of French bean (Table 1) representing a wide genetic base were studied under cold arid desert conditions of Ladakh using the randomized block design with five replications. Following the NBPGR and International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI) descriptors, the expressions on 51 morphological characters were recorded and the same were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v. 12). The results using the non-transformed data were studied in comparison to the morphological characteristics for formulation of transformation techniques, efficiency check and further confirmation through factor analysis of the principal components derived from a correlation matrix.

Results and Discussion

Genetic distances among French bean accessions estimated through a hierarchical cluster analysis of non-transformed data is presented in Figure 1. It was observed that it failed to establish the distance among the five accessions namely Pusa Parvati, FRL Sel. 1, Contender, PI 17706 and NC 67275. Moreover, the maximum genetic distance among the accessions was also comparatively lesser (7.5). Three accessions namely DARL SK-1492, DARL SK-1473 and VL Bonni 1 with high level of uniformity over the quantitative characters such as leaf length (7.9, 7.0 and 8.0 cm respectively), leaf width (5.5, 4.6 and 5.0 cm), pod length (12.2, 12.3 and 12.1 cm), pod width (1.0, 1.1 and 1.0 cm), seeds/pod (6.0 in all), number of marketable pods (18, 16 and 16), and yield/ four plants (310, 338 and 341.2 g), had clustered together. Pole bean, DARL SK-1426, Sindhu Safed and DARL BK-1034 had formed a cluster and it was evident that the pole type growth coupled with its functional quantitative characters, such as plant height, canopy width, leaf number, days to 50% flowering, days to 50% maturity, pods per plant and yield, had led to this clustering, supporting the fact that a high numerical nature of the quantitative characters leads to the masking of the equally important qualitative characters.

Data on qualitative as well as quantitative characters were brought to a common scale of zero to one by transforming it through $(\text{value of a particular character in an accession} - \text{the minimum value of that character among all accessions}) / (\text{maximum value of that character among all accessions} - \text{the minimum value of that character among all accessions})$. The clustering pattern as presented in Figure 2 shows that this methodology is more efficient in detecting the expressed genetic distances among the accessions under study, by simultaneously considering the qualitative and quantitative characters with equal weightage. This methodology was efficient in distinguishing the pole types from bushy and semi-pole types. DARL SK-1426 was altogether different from the other two pole types with its higher pod length, low yield, presence of seed mottling, higher seed width, single pod/axil and light leaf color, poor plant vigor, higher number of days required for 50% flowering, lowest number of marketable pods, lowest yield, higher single pod weight, chocolate red seed color, lowest number of branches, highest seed width, high seed weight, cream seed germination aperture with reddish brim, lowest plant height, lowest canopy width and leaf number led to the clustering of NC 67275 separately, though bushy in habit. Definitive influence of qualitative as well as quantitative characters leading to the revelation of higher level uniformity have restricted clustering on the basis of plant growth habit and its quantitative functions, resulting in the intermingling of the genetically but not highly distant bushy and semi-pole accessions.

The second transformation methodology through $(\text{value of a particular character in an accession} - \text{the mean value of that character among all accessions}) / \text{standard deviation for that character among all accessions}$ also proved to be efficient in the differentiation of pole

type cultivars from bushy and semi-pole types (Figure 3). However, identical characters of semi-pole type Sindhu Safed with respect to higher number of days for 50% flowering, leaflet width, high number of marketable pods, high yield, highest number of branches, plant height and leaf number similar to pole types had led to its clustering with pole types, showing that this methodology is more sensitive. As in the previous model, NC 67275 was found to cluster separately, closer to semi-pole types. Apart from clustering pattern in Sindhu Safed, both transformation techniques did not differ significantly and, moreover, the extent of genetic diversity revealed by both (22.5) was far higher than that obtained without transformation.

Further proof for the superiority of transformation through (value-mean)/SD was given by factor analysis of the principal components (Allard, 1960) derived from the correlation matrix (Figure 4). This again showed that Sindhu Safed, clustered with pole types because of qualitative and quantitative similarities. The higher distance of FRL Sel. 1 from the other bush types and close relationship among Pusa Parvati, Contender and VL Bonni 1 and that among DARL BK-1017 and PI 17706; and DARL SK-1473 and DARL SK-1492 were also proved.

Conclusion

Based on the assessment of genetic distances using hierarchical clustering through the transformed as well as the untransformed data and factor analysis on principal components, it could be concluded that the hierarchical cluster analysis following (value – mean)/SD transformation of qualitative and quantitative morphological data that are recorded using NBPGR or IPGRI descriptor reveal the exact genetic distance among the germplasm accessions. Thus, this methodology is devoid of the major handicap of biometric estimation of genetic variability through D^2 statistics that masks the effect of qualitative data by the quantitative data with their higher numerals. This situation is leading to wrong genetic distance and misclassifications even at the species level, as the masking of the salient qualitative factors is mitigated in the proposed unweighted hierarchical clustering.

References

- Allard, RW. Principles of Plant Breeding. John Wiley & Sons Inc.; New York: 1960.
- Chandrasekharaiah SR, Murty BR, Arunachalam V. Multivariate Analysis of Genetic Divergence in *Eu-Sorghum*. Proc Natl Inst Sci (India). 1969; 35:172–195.
- Falconer, DS. Introduction to Quantitative Genetics. Longman; London: 1989.
- Federer TW. Augmented (or *Hooniaku*) Designs. The Hawaiian Planter's Record. 1956; IV(No. 2): 191–208.
- Mahalanobis, PC. J Asiatic Soc. Vol. 25. Bengal: 1928. A Statistical Study at Chinese Head Measurement; p. 301-377.
- Mahalanobis PC. On the Generalized Distances in Statistics. Proc Natl Inst Sci (India). 1936; 2:49–55.
- Mathew, D. Doctoral Thesis. University of Agricultural Sciences; Bangalore, India: 2004. Genetic Divergence, Morphological and Molecular Characterization and Conservation of Germplasm in *Capsicum* Spp.
- Sapra, RL.; Agarwal, RC. Germplasm Evaluation: Augmented Designs. In: Rana, RS.; Sapra, RL.; Agarwal, RC.; Gambhir, R., editors. Plant Genetic Resources. Documentation and Information Management, National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources; New Delhi: 1992. p. 37-43.
- Sharma JR. Graphic Analysis and Variance Components of Flowering Time and Synchrony of Flowering in Brown Seeded Indian *Colza*. Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences. 1978; 48:437–444.
- Srivastava, U.; Mahajan, RK.; Gangopadhyay, KK.; Singh, M.; Dhillon, BS. Minimal Descriptors of Agri-Horticultural Crops, Part II: Vegetable Crops. NBPGR; New Delhi: 2001. p. 247-251.

Figure 1. Dendrogram Showing the Genetic Distances Among French Bean Accessions Using Average Linkage Between Groups in a Hierarchical Cluster Analysis Using Untransformed Data on Morphological Characters

Figure 2. Dendrogram Showing the Genetic Distances Among the French Bean Accessions Using Average Linkage Between Groups in a Hierarchical Cluster Analysis Using Untransformed Data [(value – minimum)/(maximum – minimum)] on Morphological Characters

Figure 3. Dendrogram Showing the Genetic Distances Among the French Bean Accessions Using Average Linkage Between Groups in a Hierarchical Cluster Analysis Using Untransformed Data [(value-minimum)/SD)] on Morphological Characters

Figure 4. Loading Plot on First Two Factors of on Frenchbean Accessions in Factor Analysis Extracted Through Principal Components of Correlation Matrix

Table 1
Germplasm Accessions Used in the Study, Their Growth Habit and Source

SI. No.	Accession	Growth Habit	Source
1.	Pusa Parvati	Bush (IARI), New Delhi	Indian Agricultural Research Institute
2.	Contender	Bush Resources (NBPGR), New Delhi	National Bureau of Plant Genetic
3.	VL Bonni 1	Bush	IARI, New Delhi
4.	Pole Bean	Pole	Field Research Laboratory (FRL), Leh
5.	Sindhu Safed	Semi Pole	FRL, Leh
6.	FRL Sel. 1	Bush	FRL, Leh
7.	NC 67275	Bush	Defence Agricultural Research Laboratory (DARL), Pithoragarh
8.	PI 17706	Bush	DARL, Pithoragarh
9.	DARL BK-1017	Semi Pole	DARL, Pithoragarh
10.	DARL SK-1492	Semi Pole	DARL, Pithoragarh
11.	DARL BK-1034	Pole	DARL, Pithoragarh
12.	DARL SK-1473	Semi Pole	DARL, Pithoragarh
13.	DARL SK-1426	Pole	DARL, Pithoragarh